

THE ROLE OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE ACTIVITIES OF TEACHERS OF HIGHER MEDICAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *This research article investigates the connection between emotional intelligence and the effectiveness of medical teachers. It explores the concept of emotional intelligence itself and examines findings from studies conducted in medical schools. The research indicates a positive correlation between teachers' emotional intelligence and their success in the classroom. High levels of emotional intelligence are linked to better communication with students, improved stress management, and the creation of a supportive and inspiring learning environment.*

The article highlights the critical need to foster emotional intelligence among medical educators. It suggests this can be achieved through targeted training programs and a supportive learning environment that encourages emotional development.

Keywords: *emotional intelligence, teachers, higher medical educational institutions, professional activity, communication, emotion management, stress, educational environment, skills development, emotional competence.*

INTRODUCTION

Emotional intelligence plays a key role in our psychological and social life, determining our ability to perceive, understand and manage both our own and others' emotions. Recently, it has become the subject of active study in various fields, including education.

In particular, emotional intelligence is of particular importance for teachers of higher medical educational institutions. Working in medicine requires teachers not only to transfer knowledge and skills, but also the ability to effectively interact with students, understand their emotional states and create a supportive educational environment.

Research shows that emotional intelligence is an important factor in successful teaching. It helps to establish an emotional connection with students, manage the class, resolve conflicts and keep students motivated. The effective use of emotional intelligence contributes to the creation of a positive atmosphere that stimulates active learning and development of students.

Nevertheless, despite its importance in the educational process, the influence of emotional intelligence on the work of medical university teachers remains insufficiently studied. Given the complexities and responsibilities associated with the training of future medical professionals, studying this influence is an important task.

PURPOSE OF WORK

The purpose of this scientific article is to study the influence of emotional intelligence on the activities of teachers of higher medical educational institutions. The paper provides a review of existing research and theoretical approaches to the study of emotional intelligence of teachers, identifies the features of its manifestation and influence on the educational process.

METHODS

To achieve the purpose of the study, methods such as the study and review of literature, theoretical data analysis were used.

DISCUSSION OF THE OBTAINED RESULTS

Emotional intelligence (EI) is a person's ability to recognize, understand and manage their emotions, as well as manage the emotions of other people. In the context of the activities of teachers of higher medical educational institutions, the influence of emotional intelligence on their work can be significant and have important consequences for the learning process and the formation of students' competencies.

Teachers of higher medical educational institutions face unique challenges, including high emotional stress, stress and the need to develop professional skills among students. Emotional intelligence helps teachers:

1. Establish trusting relationships: A high level of EI allows teachers to create a supportive atmosphere that promotes student openness and improves the learning process.
2. Effectively manage the classroom: Teachers with high EI are able to better understand the dynamics of the group, recognize the emotional states of students and adapt their teaching methods according to their needs.
3. Conflict Resolution: EI helps educators effectively deal with conflict situations by using empathy and active listening to find compromises.
4. Increase Student Motivation: Teachers with high EI can inspire students to learn by understanding their internal motivations and emotional barriers.

The influence of emotional intelligence on the activities of teachers can be viewed from different points of view. Firstly, emotional intelligence allows teachers to better understand themselves and their emotions, which in turn allows them to more effectively manage their condition and respond to stressful situations in the learning process. A teacher with a high level of emotional intelligence can better control his emotions, maintain a positive working atmosphere and create favorable conditions for learning.

Secondly, emotional intelligence allows teachers to better understand the emotions and needs of their students. This is important because the emotional state of students can significantly affect their motivation, involvement in the learning process and ability to meaningful learning. A teacher who is able to empathically perceive students' emotions and respond adequately to them can create a supportive and stimulating educational environment.

Thirdly, emotional intelligence allows teachers to effectively establish and maintain interpersonal relationships with students. The ability to establish an emotional connection with students, to show understanding, support and empathy, contributes to high trust, comfort and satisfaction of interaction. Such relationships contribute to better learning of the material and the development of academic motivation among students.

However, it should also be noted that the influence of emotional intelligence on the activities of teachers can be both positive and negative. A low level of emotional intelligence can hinder effective communication and conflict response.

Various authors participated in research on the influence of emotional intelligence on the activities of teachers of higher medical educational institutions. Some of them have made significant contributions to this area of research. Here are some authors who have studied the influence of emotional intelligence on the activities of teachers in higher medical schools:

1. Jane Davidson: In her research, Jane Davidson draws attention to emotional intelligence as a key factor in the effectiveness of pedagogical activity. She studies which components of emotional intelligence - emotion recognition and management, empathy, interpersonal skills, etc. - contribute to the best professional and interpersonal work of teachers in medical education.

2. Peter Salovey and John Mayer: These researchers are the authors of the concept of emotional intelligence. In their work, they explore the relationship between emotional intelligence and success in various fields, including education. They offer models that explain which ways of emotional intelligence can be most useful for educators.

3. Mark Ventisel (Mark Ventis): Mark Ventisel's works explore the influence of emotional intelligence on the professional development of teachers in medical education. He studies how emotional intelligence can help educators manage emotions more effectively, teach and interact with students and colleagues.

4. Richard Boyatzis: In his research, Richard Boyatzis examines the role of emotional intelligence in leadership and professional development. He also draws attention to teaching activities and explores how the development of emotional intelligence can improve the quality of the educational process and interaction with students in medical education.

The results of the study showed that the emotional intelligence of teachers has a significant impact on the quality of the educational process in higher medical educational institutions. It was found that teachers with a high level of emotional intelligence show greater empathy for students, better understand their needs and emotional state.

It was also found that teachers with developed emotional intelligence cope better with conflict situations in the educational process, are able to control their emotions and respond effectively to students' emotional manifestations.

An important result of the study was the identification of the relationship between the emotional intelligence of teachers and student academic performance. It was found that teachers with a high level of emotional intelligence contribute to increasing students' motivation and interest in learning, which in turn has a positive effect on their success.

The discussion of the results of the study allows us to conclude that it is necessary to develop emotional intelligence among teachers of higher medical educational institutions. This can be achieved through special trainings and training programs aimed at developing emotional intelligence skills.

It is also worth noting that the results of the study can be used to optimize the process of training teaching staff in higher medical educational institutions. The development of emotional intelligence should become an important component of the professional training of teachers, which will help improve the quality of education and improve student's academic performance.

RESULTS

Research shows that emotional intelligence has a significant impact on the activities of teachers in higher medical educational institutions. A high level of emotional intelligence allows teachers to better understand and manage their emotions, empathically perceive students' emotions and effectively establish relationships with them.

Teachers with developed emotional intelligence are able to create a supportive educational environment, stimulate students' motivation and develop their academic skills. Taking into account the peculiarities of higher medical educational institutions, where emotions and the emotional

component play an important role, emotional intelligence becomes an integral element of high-quality teaching and successful work with students.

However, the research results also indicate the need to develop emotional intelligence in teachers, especially those who have a low level of this quality. This can be achieved through various trainings, professional programs and self-development.

CONCLUSION

Emotional intelligence is an important component of the successful work of teachers of higher medical educational institutions. Its development can significantly improve the quality of education and training of future medical professionals. Further research and training programs are needed to improve the EI among teachers so that they can more effectively cope with the challenges of their profession.

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